

Master Thesis

**Role of mesoscale eddies on ventilation pathways of the South
Atlantic Ocean using Lagrangian backtracking**

Simon Schäfers

Matr. 7166528

29.10.2024

Thesis for the Degree of Master of Science in Ocean and Climate
Physics

Thesis Review: Prof. Dr. Carsten Eden
Dr. Alexa Griesel

Institute of Oceanography
Faculty of Mathematics, Informatics and Natural Sciences
University of Hamburg

Universität Hamburg
DER FORSCHUNG | DER LEHRE | DER BILDUNG

Abstract

In this thesis, I investigate how mesoscale eddies affect the ventilation timescales and pathways of South Atlantic Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) using a high-resolution ($1/10^\circ$) eddy-resolving ocean model (Parallel Ocean Program) combined with a Lagrangian particle tracking algorithm (OceanParcels). AAIW sequesters significant amounts of anthropogenic carbon along ventilation pathways within the eddy-rich Southern Ocean. The distribution of subduction zones along dynamic sections of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) suggests that ventilation may be influenced by mesoscale eddies, and not only by zonally uniform Ekman transport. To identify eddy effects, I perform particle backtracking from the AAIW interior to the mixed layer, both with eddy-resolving model output and its mean state, excluding mesoscale eddy velocities and associated mixed layer variations. Eddy effects increase the contribution of Drake Passage waters to the South Atlantic AAIW and reduce mean age estimates by 8.6 years, attributable to accelerated advection together with deeper and more southward subduction near the Malvinas Confluence Zone. Eddies also modulate ventilation pathways by reducing transport through the Agulhas Leakage, facilitating downwelling in eddy-rich regions, and enabling crossing the Subantarctic Front (SAF) between the Southern and Atlantic Oceans. This thesis highlights the role of eddies in the ventilation of the pycnocline, which, if accurately represented, increase estimates of ventilation rates and cold water inflow, enhancing Southern Ocean carbon and heat uptake in ocean models.

Contents

1 Introduction	3
2 Methods	6
2.1 Model	6
2.2 AAIW Definition	6
2.3 Eddy-Mean Flow Decomposition	8
2.3.1 Horizontal Velocity	9
2.3.2 Mixed Layer Depth	10
2.4 Lagrangian Tracking Algorithm	12
2.5 Inverse Gaussian PDF	13
2.6 Water Mass Properties	14
2.7 Experimental Setups	14
3 Results	15
3.1 Particle Subduction	15
3.2 Transit Times	17
3.3 Subduction Zones	19
3.3.1 Transit Times	19
3.3.2 Depth Distribution	21
3.4 Diapycnal Component	22
3.5 Ventilation Pathways	23
3.5.1 Pathways by Subduction Zones	24
3.6 Particle Velocities	26
4 Summary and Discussion	29
5 Conclusions and Prospects	32
A Sensitivity Experiment ED05/ED05_{MLD}	36
A.1 Subduction Locations	36
A.2 Transit Times by Subduction Zones	37
B Subduction with Surface Condition	37
C Orbiting Particles	38

1 Introduction

The Southern Ocean plays a crucial role in the climate system, accounting for almost half of the oceanic carbon uptake (Khatiwala et al., 2009) and thus delaying climate warming. Here, cold and fresh water masses subduct below the mixed layer, withdrawing excessive CO₂ and heat from the atmosphere. These water masses spread northwards to form the Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) at depths between 500 and 1500m (Talley, 2011). In this depth range, the pycnocline separates the light surface waters from the dense deep and bottom waters. The transport of water masses from the well-mixed surface layer into the AAIW is recognized as the ventilation of the pycnocline.

AAIW ventilation is linked to the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC), driven by strong westerly winds. The ACC, as widely unimpeded by zonal boundaries, develops strong and deep fronts. Of these fronts, the Subantarctic Front (SAF) and the Polar Front (PF) mark its northern and southern extents. The ACC is the strongest global current system, with an estimated transport of 140 Sv at its narrowest extension, the Drake Passage (Macdonald and Wunsch, 1996).

East of the Drake Passage, the Southern Ocean interacts with the South Atlantic along the SAF near 50°S (Fig. 1.1b; Talley, 2011). The Malvinas Confluence Zone (MCZ) in the west and the Agulhas Retroflexion Zone (ARZ) in the east are two highly dynamic regions that regulate this exchange. In the MCZ, the Brazil Current converges with a cold and fresh branch of the ACC, before both flow eastward (Gordon, 1989). In the ARZ, the Agulhas Current surpasses the African continent and merges with the eastward flow of the ACC. This interaction generates Agulhas Rings, that separate from the current and transport warm, haline water masses from the Indian Ocean into the South Atlantic (Bennett, 1988).

(a) Idealized zonally averaged schematic of the overturning pathways into the mode and intermediate water layers (shaded in yellow). The blue and orange pathways make up the upper overturning cell, and the purple and green pathways make up the subtropical overturning cell. The blue and purple pathways pass through the mixed layer (blue shading) and subduct across the base of the mixed layer, whereas the orange and green pathways are transformed diabatically in the interior. *from Morrison et al. (2022)*

(b) South Atlantic Ocean surface circulation schematics. Malvinas Confluence Zone (MCZ) in the west and Agulhas Retroflexion Zone (ARZ) to the east connect the South Atlantic to Southern and Indian Ocean. The Subantarctic Front marks the northern extend of the ACC. *from Talley (2011)*

Figure 1.1

The wind stress curl of the westerlies induces northward Ekman transport¹ on the surface layer of the ACC. As those cold and dense water masses cross the SAF, they subduct below the light surface waters, which results in downward-sloping isopycnals towards the north (Fig. 1.1a; Morrison et al., 2022). The combination of strong currents and sloping isopycnals induces baroclinic instability, resulting in meanders and mesoscale eddies at the edges of the fronts. These mesoscale eddies contain most of the kinetic energy (KE) in the ACC (Trani et al., 2014).

AAIW ventilation is often idealized by the Ekman-induced meridional overturning, a relatively uniform process, as driven by the westerlies (Andrews and McIntyre, 1976). However, observations indicate that subduction is localized and seasonal, driven not only by Ekman transport but also lateral advection² and eddy fluxes (Sallée et al., 2012). Contributing to subduction, eddy effects are likely to further influence the ventilation pathways, which link the subducted water masses to the AAIW core.

The route and current velocities of ventilation pathways determine the transit time from the mixed layer to the AAIW core. These transit time distributions (TTD) are often estimated with an Inverse Gaussian probability density function (PDF), which characterizes the distribution by mean age and width. A lower mean age in the TTD indicates faster carbon uptake (Morrison et al., 2022), while the width of the TTD serves as an estimation of diffusivity along the pathway (D. Waugh et al., 2006; Chouksey et al., 2022).

Eddies influence these ventilation pathways by inducing isopycnal mixing, which allows water to move independent from the mean flow, and thus, enables meridional transport in the zonal regime of the ACC. (Balwada et al., 2016). Apart from isopycnal pathways induced by mean flow or eddies, diapycnal pathways seem to contribute to ventilation at a comparable magnitude (Fig. 1.1a; Katsumata et al., 2013).

Both subduction and ventilation challenge observational campaigns, as subduction is located offshore in the Southern Ocean, and ventilation acts over large spatial and temporal scales. Observations often rely on estimating outflows from the mixed layer or tracking passive tracers like anthropogenic carbon (Sallée et al., 2010; D. Waugh et al., 2006). Dynamical ocean models complement the understanding of AAIW ventilation. Ventilation pathways can be reconstructed by monitoring tracer diffusion and transport, or particle advection, in models. Here, the Lagrangian framework, which traces moving particles over time, provides more insights into transit times and exact trajectories compared to Eulerian frameworks, which focus on fixed locations.

For the South Atlantic AAIW, distinct ventilation pathways are identified, primarily passing through the Drake Passage or the Agulhas Leakage. While the two contributing water masses have similar densities, they differ in temperature and salinity, defining a cold (Drake Passage) and a warm (Agulhas Leakage) route (e.g. Rühls et al., 2019; Olivé Abelló, 2023). Lagrangian backtracking, which traces particle backward to their subduction location, has revealed subduction zones "near the Agulhas Retroflexion, south of New Zealand, west of the Drake Passage, and east of Brazil in the Argentine Basin" (Chouksey et al., 2022). These subduction locations partially match the localized subduction identified with observations (Sallée et al., 2012) and tracer simulations (Jones et al., 2016). However, the effects of eddies on these ventilation pathways remain uncertain.

¹(surface) Ekman transport describes movement of surface water perpendicular to the wind direction, caused by the Earth's rotation. The deflection is anti-cyclonic, i.e. counter-clockwise in the Southern Hemisphere.

²Subduction by lateral advection describes the horizontal flow out of a seasonal, deep mixed layer when a shallower mixed layer establishes after the winter (Stommel, 1979).

Understanding eddy effects is mandatory for improving mesoscale eddy parameterizations in coarse ocean models, especially in the Southern Ocean and at the margins of the South Atlantic, where mesoscale eddies hold the majority of kinetic energy. Common parameterizations, such as the Gent-McWilliams coefficient for eddy-induced advection (Gent and McWilliams, 1990) and the Redi coefficient for isopycnal mixing (Redi, 1982) often fall short of representing eddy effects, particularly with recent changes in atmospheric forcing (Farneti et al., 2010; Hogg et al., 2015). Further, resolving eddy activity instead of parameterizing it has shown a reduced transport through the Agulhas Leakage (Rühs et al., 2019).

Recent model experiments highlight how eddy effects can impact ventilation. In contrast to a mean flow field, resolving eddy motion increases tracer diffusion (Kamenkovich et al., 2017) and alters the transport across the ACC (McAulfield, 2019). Building on these results, this thesis contrasts eddying and mean flow, using Lagrangian backtracking to investigate the effect of eddies on the distribution of transit times and related ventilation in the South Atlantic AAIW.

Research Questions and Outline

1. **How do eddy effects change the origin of South Atlantic AAIW?**
2. **Do eddy effects increase or decrease the mean age and width of the South Atlantic AAIW TTD?**
3. **What are the eddy effects on ventilation pathways into the South Atlantic AAIW?**

This thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 2 describes the model with its AAIW representation and establishes a mean state to compare to the eddying model output. I further introduce the Lagrangian backtracking algorithm and the Inverse Gaussian distribution, and define experiments over which to perform the particle tracking. Chapter 3 includes results obtained by particle backtracking over the defined experiments. Here, I identify sources of origin with distinct mean ages and widths for particles advected by eddying and mean flow. Further, I estimate the sensitivity to the representation of mixed layer depth. Subsequently, I consider the particle trajectories and velocities, empathizing regions where they deviate between eddying and mean flow. I compare the results with observations and model experiments in chapter 4 and conclude the implications of this thesis in chapter 5.

2 Methods

2.1 Model

I use the $1/10^\circ$ global tripole Parallel Ocean Program (POP) model, which features 42 unequally spaced vertical levels extending to a depth of 5874m. The grid is the structured Arakawa B grid. The model is based on primitive equations, with Boussinesq and hydrostatic approximations. The model resolves the large-scale ocean circulation and permits mesoscale eddies, as the first baroclinic Rossby radius, a measure for eddy length scales in mid to high latitudes (Eden, 2007; Moreton et al., 2020) exceeds the grid size. In this thesis, I focus on the region between 20°S and 70°S , where the Rossby radius ranges from 60km at 20°S to 10km at 70°S (Chelton et al., 1998). The grid size in this region ranges from 10km at 20°S to 4km at 70°S .

The model is initialized using the ocean state from Maltrud et al., 2010, which was integrated for 120 years using annually repeating normal-year Coordinated Ocean-Ice Reference Experiments (CORE) surface forcing (Large and Yeager, 2004). In 1983, the model transitioned to interannually varying CORE forcing (Large and Yeager, 2009) and integrated for an additional 27 years. The available model output spans the years 1985-2009, and I focus on the period 2000-2009 to exclude the model spin-up period and facilitate comparisons with other studies (e.g., Rhs et al., 2019; Chouksey et al., 2022).

I use daily model output, specifically 3D velocities for particle advection and the mixed layer depth (MLD) as the depth where particles start subducting. In the POP model, the MLD is defined "as the shallowest depth where the local, interpolated buoyancy gradient matches the maximum buoyancy gradient between the surface and any discrete depth within that water column." (Smith et al., 2010; Large et al., 1997) The POP model uses a KPP parameterization (Large et al., 1994) for the mixed layer, so that model output velocities inside it do not fully represent the mixed layer dynamics. Particle trajectories are therefore only considered until their first mixed layer contact.

The mean temperature model output over the period 2000-2009 is used to calculate the SAF as the 5°C isotherm, and the PF as the 2°C isotherm at 200m depth (Talley, 2011). Daily temperature and salinity model output is used to calculate potential density, enabling an assessment of the diapycnal component of a particle trajectory. Furthermore, potential density is used to define the AAIW, where the particles are released and backtracked from. In the following sections, I describe the AAIW derived from the model output, compare it to observational data, and define the particle release area.

2.2 AAIW Definition

To identify the AAIW in the POP model, I apply the definition of potential density range between $1026.82\text{-}1027.43\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$ (Ingmanson and Wallace, 1995) on the mean potential density model output over the period 2000-2009. For reference, I use the WOCE-Argo Global Hydrographic Climatology (WAGHC; Gouretski, 2018), which provides interpolated observational data for the period 1985-2016. As for the model output, I define the observational AAIW by potential density calculated from temperature and salinity.

The expansion of AAIW is illustrated along the longitude of 25°W , close to the WOCE A16 section in the South Atlantic, superimposed on salinity and temperature (Fig. 2.1). In both observations and model output, the AAIW within the σ_0 contours of 26.82 and $27.43\text{kg}/\text{m}^3$ reaches up to the surface south of 50°S . The depth of the upper limiting isopycnal increases towards lower latitudes and reaches its maximum depth of about 500m at 30°S . The lower limiting isopycnal has a depth of 500m at 50°S , which

Figure 2.1: AAIW potential density contours (white) superimposed to salinity (a,c) and temperature (b,d) for a meridional section along 25°W. (a,b) calculated from observations (WOCE 1985-2016) and (b,d) from the POP model output of the years 2000-2009. The red lines indicate the depth levels for particle release (on 35-40°S, 60°W-20°E).

increases steeply towards lower latitudes, reaching a maximum depth of about 1500m at 40°S. From 30°S towards the equator, the AAIW maintains its width but slowly decreases in depth.

The AAIW density definition corresponds to a salinity minimum between 33.8-34.4 g/kg , which is strongly pronounced near the surface in high latitudes (Fig. 2.1a,c). In lower latitudes, especially north of 30°S, the AAIW salinity is significantly lower than the high salinity of the Subantarctic Surface and Mode Waters (SASW/SAMW). However, in low latitudes, the AAIW salinity minimum is reduced to 34.2-34.6 g/kg (compare Talley, 2011). Within the AAIW density definition, the temperature ranges from 2-6°C (Fig. 2.1b,d). Similar to the AAIW isopycnals, these temperature contours also increase in depth with decreasing latitudes. Within the AAIW isopycnals, the temperature increases from surface to ocean interior and is distinguishable from the colder Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW) and the warm SASW and SAMW (Fig. 2.1b,c).

The seawater properties and hence the extent of the AAIW show a general agreement between observations and the model output. However, in contrast to the modeled AAIW, the observed AAIW isopycnals are more tilted between 40 and 50°S, resulting in a deeper AAIW at mid-latitudes (Fig. 2.1a,b). Here, the observed AAIW ranges from 500 to 1600m at 40°S, whereas the modeled AAIW ranges from 250 to 1400m at the same latitude (Fig. 2.1c,d). Furthermore, the observed salinity minimum shows a salinity $<34g/kg$ following the slope of the AAIW, which the model AAIW does not maintain beyond 250m depth (Fig. 2.1a,c).

I define the AAIW core at the latitudes of its greatest extent, i.e. between 35-40°S, excluding potential variability at higher latitudes and the decreasing intensity of the salinity minimum towards the equator. For particle release within the AAIW core, I use 5 depth levels of the model grid, which lie in a depth range of 400-1200m (Fig. 2.1c,d).

2.3 Eddy-Mean Flow Decomposition

I examine the eddy effects on AAIW formation by contrasting the velocity fields from the POP eddying model output with a mean velocity field that excludes eddy effects. The eddy effects include coherent eddies, and meanders, which are not confined to a seasonal cycle and do not persist over annual to decadal time scales. To retain a seasonal cycle, I define the mean field as the 10-year average over the years 2000-2009 for every day t of a given year. With the mean field defined, I separate the model output velocity into mean flow ($\bar{\mathbf{u}}$) and eddy perturbation (\mathbf{u}'):

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \bar{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{u}'(t) \quad (1)$$

Subsequently, the kinetic energy of model output (KE) and mean field (MKE) are defined by the horizontal velocities:

$$KE(t) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{u}_h^2(t), \quad MKE = \frac{1}{2} \bar{\mathbf{u}}_h^2(t) \quad (2)$$

I calculate the total KE and MKE for each day of the year (Fig. 2.2). KE and MKE are calculated at the depth level closest to 400m as it marks the upper limit of AAIW in mid-latitudes and aligns with typical MLDs north of the ACC during Austral winter (see below 2.3.2). Therefore, the chosen depth is appropriate for representing the dynamics along the ventilation pathways from subduction until entering the AAIW. I average KE and MKE over all longitudes and latitudes from 35°S to 65°S, covering dynamic regions relevant to AAIW ventilation pathways, such as the ACC, the MCZ, and the ARZ. As the grid area decreases with latitude, I weigh the local KE values by the grid area they represent.

Figure 2.2: KE and MKE of 2000-2009 at 381m depth, averaged over 35-65°S and 180°E-180°W. KE and MKE are calculated for each day in the year, following eq. 2. MKE is displayed on a separate y-axis that is reduced by 80 cm^2/s^2 .

The daily MKE of the years 2000-2009 ranges between 46 and 51 cm^2/s^2 , exhibiting a seasonal cycle that results in a decrease in kinetic energy from September to January. With a relative difference of about 5% between the maximum and minimum values, the influence of seasonal variations on the averaged MKE at 400m depth is low, but significant. In contrast, the KE during the same period is approximately three times as large as the MKE, with annual mean values ranging from 134.6 to 144.5 cm^2/s^2 and daily values fluctuating between 127 and 152 cm^2/s^2 . The KE is generally highest in the first half of the year, dropping at the onset of Austral summer. However, the KE does not exhibit a consistent pattern. Its variations cannot be linked to a specific climate mode or the state of a single dynamic region when averaged over a broad area.

The year with the highest KE is 2004, while 2005 exhibits the lowest KE. Consequently, I select the year 2004 for comparison with the mean state and 2005 for a sensitivity test. I refer to the 2004 (2005) model output as ED04 (ED05) and the 10-year average for each day of the year as MEAN. The separation of MKE from KE reveals that the MEAN velocity field contains only about one-third of the kinetic energy compared to the model output velocity fields. This discrepancy primarily arises from the attenuation of time-dependent extreme velocities through averaging. In the next step, I will consider velocity snapshots of ED04 and MEAN.

2.3.1 Horizontal Velocity

I compare the ED04 with the MEAN absolute horizontal velocity fields for one day in Austral and winter (Fig. 2.3) close to 400m depth. The SAF and PF, defined by isotherms, highlight the ACC. The MEAN velocity snapshot shows strong velocities within and north of the ACC, most pronounced between the Cape of Good Hope and New Zealand with up to 30 cm/s (Fig. 2.3a). Instead of exhibiting eddying behavior, the MEAN velocities show a jet-like behavior along the ACC track. While meanders are present, particularly around the ARZ, the MCZ, and in the South Pacific, they show a coarse structure with insignificant movement outside the main currents. The MEAN velocities display the Agulhas Leakage into the South Atlantic as a weak current towards the northwest with indistinguishable eddy structures. The Agulhas Current shows as a narrow current without eddy features, that originates from north and south of Madagascar. Outside the main currents, the MEAN velocities decrease below values of 1 cm/s , particularly in the South Pacific, where flow is largely confined to the ACC.

The ED04 velocity snapshot shows the ACC, which extends from the Cape of Good Hope, passing south of New Zealand and through the Drake Passage, back into the South Atlantic. The ACC in ED04 exhibits eddying and meandering structures with velocities exceeding 50 cm/s , especially in the ARZ (Fig. 2.3c). Notably, the Agulhas Leakage shows distinct Agulhas Rings with high velocities of about 50 cm/s propagating into the South Atlantic. Likewise, in the Mozambique Channel, distinct eddies prevent a continuous flow. Outside the main currents, weaker eddy structures are observable throughout the ocean basins, with velocities around 0.1 m/s .

Figure 2.3: Absolute horizontal velocity snapshots (Aug 15) at 381m depth for (a) MEAN and (c) ED04. Yellow circumpolar contours mark the position of SAF and PF. Distribution of directional horizontal velocities at 381m depth, between 35-65°S for (b) MEAN and (d) ED04. White x marks the overall mean velocity.

As indicated by the KE (section 2.2), the absolute velocities are greater in ED04 than in MEAN (Fig. 2.3b,d), even though both experiments have a similar mean zonal ($\sim 3\text{cm/s}$) and meridional ($\sim 0\text{cm/s}$). In ED04, eastward velocities can reach up to 50 cm/s, while westward velocities extend to about 30 cm/s. MEAN velocities, in contrast, reach only about 60% of the ED04 values. Both experiments show a bias toward positive (eastward) zonal velocities due to the ACC's influence. In ED04, westward velocities are around 60% as strong as eastward velocities. This imbalance is even more pronounced in MEAN, where westward velocities rarely exceed 15 cm/s, especially when combined with meridional movement (Fig. 2.3b). The un-obstructed ACC flow creates a net positive velocity, which, on average is equal for ED04 and MEAN. However, ED04 eddies effects produce a wider velocity range, including higher and also opposing velocities.

The comparison between the ED04 and MEAN velocity fields highlights several key differences that are likely to influence particle transport. The less structured and weaker ACC in the MEAN field contrasts with the eddy-rich behavior seen in ED04. The MEAN flow shows strong velocity gradients between the ACC fronts and the nearly motionless ocean basins, especially the Pacific Ocean. In contrast, the ED04 velocities show eddy features surpassing the interface between ACC fronts and ocean basins. Furthermore, the dynamics in key passages like the ARZ differ greatly between the two velocity fields. In ED04, the Agulhas Leakage displays distinct, propagating Agulhas Rings, whereas in MEAN, it shows a weak, continuous flow. Similarly, the MCZ shows a less structured and weaker flow in MEAN compared to the meandering, eddy-dominated structure in ED04. Since both the ARZ and MCZ are crossed by AAIW ventilation pathways, changes in the regions' dynamics are likely to influence AAIW formation.

In addition to the velocity, I perform the 10-year average over the years 2000-2009 for every day t of a given year on MLD, salinity, and temperature. Averaging the velocities shows to decrease the variance and distinct structures, which also applies to the other model output variables. Given that water submerging below the mixed layer defines subduction, a closer examination of the MLD in ED04 and MEAN is necessary.

2.3.2 Mixed Layer Depth

The representation of MLD is important for estimating subduction in Lagrangian backtracking. Changes in the MLD can influence both transit time and subduction location. For instance, in Austral winter, MLDs with locally deep maxima may cause passing-by particles to enter the mixed layer horizontally. With subduction defined by the mixed layer crossing, this would complete the particle's pathway from the mixed layer to the AAIW core. Conversely, if the MLD has low variability and lacks deep maxima, the same particle might stay below the mixed layer throughout the winter, extending its transit time. While averaging the MLD does not change the mean values, it does reduce variance, similar to the effect seen for velocities (see Fig. 2.3). Thus, understanding the differences between the MLD obtained from ED04 and MEAN, as well as a comparison to observations, is essential before using mixed layer crossing as a criterion for subduction.

I compare the MLDs of MEAN and ED04 with the ocean mixed layer thickness of the WAGHC dataset, which is defined by temperature (Gouretski, 2018). The WAGHC MLD has a resolution of $1/4^\circ$ and is available as a monthly mean, while the MEAN and ED04 MLDs have a daily output with $1/10^\circ$ resolution. As the mixed layer shows the greatest depths at the end of Austral winter, I compare the August WAGHC MLD with the MLDs of MEAN and ED04 on August 15 (see Fig. 2.4).

Figure 2.4: Mixed layer depth in Austral winter (August) calculated with (a) WAGHC (monthly mean 1985-2016), (c) MEAN, and (e) ED04 (both for Aug 15). Black circumpolar contours mark the position of SAF and PF. Diamonds exemplarily show different MLD regimes in the Drake Passage (red), the central South Atlantic (magenta), and South of Australia (orange). (b,d,f) show the annual MLD variation for these points for observations, MEAN, and ED04. Gray shading in (b) and dashed, black lines in (d,f) indicate the time step shown in (a,c,e).

All winter mixed layers show regional patterns with a depth larger than 300m, which are restricted to the eastern Pacific and south of Australia. Both deep mixed layer regions are located directly north of the SAF (Fig. 2.4a,c,e). Outside these areas, the MLD ranges between 50 and 200m, with deeper patterns in the central and western Pacific, as well as the South Atlantic. As expected when comparing coarse, monthly averaged to highly resolved daily values, the observed MLD shows less extreme MLDs compared to MEAN and ED04 (Fig. 2.4a). Here, the deep mixed layers along the SAF show maximum values of 500m, while MEAN reaches 600m and ED04 exceeds 700m depth at the same location. Apart from the absolute values, the WAGHC MLD shows partly differing patterns in the South Atlantic, compared to the POP model output. While MEAN and ED04 show comparably deep MLDs of about 250m depth at the western boundary of the South Atlantic, those are shifted towards the southeast in observations, aligning with the northern edge of the SAF. Further, extremely deep MLDs in MEAN and ED04, exceeding 600m east of the Drake Passage, are strongly reduced in the observational MLD.

Comparing the MEAN to the ED04 MLD reveals a close agreement, with the resolution of small features as a major difference. The MEAN MLD exhibits gradually changing depths, exemplarily seen west of the Drake Passage (Fig. 2.4c). In contrast, the ED04 MLD shows strong gradients with instantaneous changes in MLD of up to 500m. Further, eddy features in ED04 encapsulate deeper mixed layers than the surrounding water columns, most prominently seen within Agulhas Rings (Fig. 2.4e). As for velocities, the ED04 MLD exhibits more extreme, namely deeper values, which shows in the central Southern Pacific.

Considering the annual cycle of local MLDs confirms a strong seasonality, as winter MLDs exceed the summer MLDs by an order of magnitude (Fig. 2.4b,d,f). Remarkably, the increase of depth in Austral autumn does not align among the locations, while the re-stratification in Austral spring does. In the Drake Passage and south of Australia, where deep mixed layers are present, the modeled MLD exceeds the observed by up to 300 meters. For the South Atlantic, close to the SAF, however, the observed MLD is deeper than MEAN and ED04 at all times (Fig. 2.4b).

The strong gradients in the ED04 MLD compared to the gradually changing MEAN MLD also show in the annual cycle. Collapse and re-stratification can occur within days for the ED04, while the MEAN MLD decreases and rebuilds within two to three months (Fig. 2.4d,f). In ED04, jumps of over 500m depth indicate the transit of eddies or shifts in the fronts. For the locations selected, the ED04 MLD maximum depths are about 100-200m deeper than the MEAN MLD.

The different MLDs for MEAN and ED04 affect the estimation of subduction in Lagrangian backtracking. Fronts and eddy features influence the local MLD, so using a coarse or averaged MLD would reduce the accuracy of estimating subduction. At the same time, the ED04 MLD shows deeper maxima of MLD and faster collapse and re-stratification. Comparing subduction for different MLDs may therefore raise systematic errors, like a shift in seasonality. To account for both issues and estimate the effect of an averaged MLD, I estimate ED04 subduction with both the "eddy-influenced" ED04 and the averaged MEAN MLD. Before defining these experiments, I introduce the particle tracking algorithm, which requires both velocity and MLD fields to compute particle trajectories. Further, I define the Inverse Gaussian fit and the density deviation for analyzing particle transit times and water mass properties.

2.4 Lagrangian Tracking Algorithm

I use a Lagrangian tracking algorithm based on the Ocean Parcels toolbox (Delandmeter and Van Sebille, 2019). The algorithm iteratively changes particle position and properties defined in a Particle Set, based on a Field Set that contains 4D fields of velocity and water mass properties, i.e. temperature, salinity, and MLD. The change in particle position and properties is calculated using customizable kernels. For this study, I use a kernel for advection and a kernel recording properties at the position of the particle, next to supplementary kernels, maintaining smooth computation.

The Field Set provides velocities and properties at each particle position by linear interpolation from the surrounding grid points. Further, it incorporates the grid type of the fields used, which, is an Arakawa B-grid for the POP model. The initial position of the particles in the Particle Set is based on the particle release area in Fig. 2.1, a spatial box within the density-defined AAIW. I initialize a particle at every 10th grid point within the particle release area, to optimize computational cost. The particles are not released at one time step but monthly over the first year of tracking. This prevents an exceeding influence of one seasonal flow characteristic on the advection of all particles. The POP model grid has unevenly distributed depth levels, so the volume a particle represents can vary significantly. To ensure realistic transports and statistical distributions, I weigh the particles by the volume of the grid cells on which they were released. In total, the Particle Set contains $21,537 \times 12 = 258,444$ particles.

In each time step of the tracking algorithm, kernels advect each particle, track the properties at their positions, and manage errors occurring along boundaries. The first, predefined, kernel (AdvectionRK-3D) modifies the particle position based on the Runge-Kutta 4 method, i.e. computes the particle advection. The second kernel (SampleProps) tracks the MLD, temperature, and salinity at the position of the particle. One supplementary kernel (PeriodicBC) ensures zonal periodic boundary conditions by modifying the position of parcels that surpass the Fieldset dimensions in zonal direction (at 0° and 360°).

Another supplementary kernel (CopeErrors) deletes particles that leave the defined field in meridional or vertical direction. This can happen if a particle gets close to the equator or, by numerical error, passes the ocean surface. In an Arakawa B-grid, particles can also get trapped at topographic boundaries. If a particle is trapped, i.e. has not moved for 30 days, it is also deleted. As shown below, about 1 in 10 particles are trapped before reaching the mixed layer (Tab. 3.1). Trapping occurs more frequently in boundary currents than in the open ocean, which can distort volumetric transport estimates. Additionally, particles that fail to reach the mixed layer can not be included for the calculation of mean water mass age, leading to an underestimation of mean age. Ensuring an equally distributed and low number of these excluded particles across experiments is essential for maintaining comparability.

The particles are advected and tracked with a time step of 24 hours and a total run time of 120 years. The tracking algorithm has to restart after each simulated year, due to limited computation time. The last particle positions and properties of a completed computation are used to initialize the restarting tracking algorithm. For every experiment in Tab. 2.1, I perform 120 iterations with consecutive particle initialization to reach a total advection time of 120 years.

2.5 Inverse Gaussian PDF

To determine the mean age and width of a particle transit time distribution (pTTD), I fit an Inverse Gaussian probability density function (PDF), which is used in tracer analyses and shows to be an appropriate estimate for Lagrangian particle tracking (D. W. Waugh et al., 2004; Chouksey et al., 2022):

$$G(\tau, \Gamma, \Delta) = \sqrt{\frac{\Gamma^3}{4\pi\Delta^2\tau^3}} \exp\left[-\frac{\Gamma(\tau - \Gamma)^2}{4\Delta^2\tau}\right]. \quad (3)$$

G is a solution for a one-dimensional advection-diffusion equation, assuming a singular, but diffusive process. G estimates the mean age Γ and the width Δ of a distribution. The width Δ indicates the diffusivity, increasing values displace the peak from the mean age to lower values. In the case of AAIW formation, fitting the Inverse Gaussian distribution assumes one uniform subduction process with a comparable pathway. I use a relative Root Mean Square Error ϵ between G and the pTTD to assess the quality of the fit and, consequently, evaluate the validity of single-source AAIW formation:

$$\epsilon = \sqrt{n^{-1} \sum_i^n \left(\frac{G_i - \chi_i}{N_{particles}}\right)^2}, \quad (4)$$

with the fitted G , χ the values of the pTTD histogram for n bins, and $N_{particles}$ the number of particles incorporated by the pTTD. I fix the mean age Γ to the pTTD mean, allowing only the width Δ to be fitted, as otherwise, the fit tends to overestimate Γ by up to 20 years. While a higher mean age than calculated over the pTTD is realistic, since approximately one-fifth of the particles may still reach the mixed layer after 120 years (see Tab. 3.1), fixing Γ prevents incomprehensible fits and ensures comparability among experiments.

2.6 Water Mass Properties

In addition to the age of the water mass, different source regions also contribute distinct water mass properties. Considering temperature and salinity at the time of subduction is useful for two reasons. Firstly, water originating from these regions contributes to the composition of the target water mass, which plays an important role in the estimation of the thermohaline circulation (Rühs et al., 2019). Secondly, estimating the density at the subduction location can indicate whether the pathway connecting the source region to the AAIW is predominantly isopycnal or diapycnal. In the POP model, diffusion is parameterized, accordingly, the majority of movement should be along isopycnals. However, diapycnal movement can occur due to spurious, numerical mixing. To estimate the diapycnal component of a trajectory between subduction and AAIW core, I define the density deviation of a particle

$$\Delta\sigma_0 = |\sigma_0(AAIW) - \sigma_0(SUB)| \quad (5)$$

as the absolute difference in potential density between release in the AAIW and mixed layer contact.

2.7 Experimental Setups

EXP.	Velocity field	MLD criterion
MEAN	repeated annual cycles with 2000-2009 day-to-day mean velocity field	2000-2009 day to day mean MLD
ED04	repeated annual cycles for year 2004 total velocity field	2000-2009 day to day mean MLD
ED04 _{MLD}	repeated annual cycles for year 2004 total velocity field	2004 daily "eddy-influenced" MLD
ED05 (Appendix)	repeated annual cycles for year 2005 total velocity field	2000-2009 day to day mean MLD
ED05 _{MLD} (Appendix)	repeated annual cycles for year 2005 total velocity field	2005 daily "eddy-influenced" MLD

Table 2.1: Experimental setups. Second column indicates the velocity field with which the particle backtracking is done, third column indicates the criterion used to determine to which depth the particles are backtracked.

3 Results

In this section, I will describe the subduction locations and transit times for MEAN, ED04, and ED04_{MLD}, highlighting key differences between them. The subduction locations can be clustered into subduction zones which show differences between experiments regarding their relative contribution, transit times, and associated water mass properties. To propose an explanation for the observed differences, I examine eddy contributions to particle pathways and velocities.

All experiments exhibit a similar distribution of included and excluded particles (Tab. 3.1). Specifically, between 65.5% and 71.3% of particles reached the mixed layer within 120 years, while 16.8% to 20.7% did not. Additionally, 12.0% to 13.9% of particles were deleted by the tracking algorithm. Notably, 8.2% more particles reached the mixed layer in MEAN compared to ED04, despite lower velocities. This changes with the different MLD configuration, here the included particles of ED04_{MLD} slightly exceed those in MEAN by 1.6%. Out of 258,444 seeded particles, I can analyze between 179,765 and 193,460 subducted particles in each experiment.

Experiment	Mixed layer crossing		No mixed layer crossing		Trapped or left domain	
	%	<i>N</i>	%	<i>N</i>	%	<i>N</i>
MEAN	70.20	191910	17.84	39143	11.95	27391
ED04	65.47	179765	20.68	45754	13.85	32925
ED04 _{MLD}	71.29	193460	16.76	36751	11.95	28233

Table 3.1: Volume weighted percentage and absolute number of advected particles for which: subduction was identified (Mixed layer crossing); no subduction was identified during the 120-year advection (No mixed layer crossing); got deleted before possible subduction due to numerical error (Trapped or left domain), for the experiments considered in this thesis.

3.1 Particle Subduction

I determine the subduction location of all particles that have reached the mixed layer in the Lagrangian backtracking framework. To depict the horizontal distribution, I bin all subduction locations on a 2x2° grid (Fig. 3.1a,c,e). Further, I show the spatial distribution of subduction locations (Fig. 3.1b,d,f).

The distribution of particle subduction locations shows an overall comparable pattern in all experiments (Fig. 3.1a,c,e). Most particles reach the mixed layer around the Drake Passage (DP), indicating it to be a prominent subduction zone. North of the SAF, several other subduction zones are visible. In the South Atlantic (SA) and South Indian Ocean (SI), subduction zones lie between 20 and 40°S. In the South Pacific Ocean (SP), the subduction locations are located more southward between 40 and 50°S. The boxes separating the subduction zones will be defined and discussed in detail in section 3.3. Particle subduction within DP, SI, and SP strongly overlaps with the deep winter MLDs, indicating a seasonal subduction and a lateral transport out of the mixed layer. In contrast, the SA subduction zone is not connected to a deep winter MLD but still overlaps with the maximum MLD within the South Atlantic. The different subduction zones imply varying travel distances for particles, suggesting that their transit times between the mixed layer and Atlantic AAIW also differ.

The presence of different subduction zones appears in the meridional distribution of subduction locations (Fig. 3.1d). In all experiments, a bimodal distribution is visible, with one peak around 55°S and a second, smaller peak around 35°S. The southern peak reflects DP and SP subduction zones, while the

northern peak corresponds to the SA and SI subduction zones. South of Australia, however, the SI subduction zone extends beyond 50°, following the SAF and partially contributing to the southern peak.

In the zonal distribution, the amount of particles subducting at longitudes around 60°W, where the DP and SA subduction zones overlap, is by an order of magnitude larger than in other subduction zones (Fig. 3.1b). Other concentrations of particle subduction are located between 120-150°W (SP), around 0° (SA), and between 60-180°E (SI). Remarkably, areas at 170°W, 110°W, and 40°E show little to no subduction. Similar to the lateral distributions, the distribution of subduction depth is heterogeneous and influenced by the different subduction zones (Fig. 3.1f). In MEAN and ED04, approximately 30% of the particles subduct within the upper 200m, indicating a shallow mixed layer. The remaining particles subduct at depths coarsely distributed around 400m, with some extending up to 800m. Winter mixed layers deeper than 300m are only present in the subduction zones of DP and SI (see Fig. 2.4d), while SA winter MLDs rarely exceed depths of 200m.

Figure 3.1: Left: Subduction locations for (a) MEAN, (c) ED04, and (e) ED04_{MLD}. The circumpolar red line marks the SAF. Black boxes show subduction zones: SP (35-70°S, 120-180°W), DP (45-70°S, 40-110°W), SA (20-45°S, 30°E-50°W), and SI (20-55°S, 40-180°E). Right: (b) zonal (logarithmic), (d) meridional, and (e) vertical distribution of subduction locations for MEAN (red), ED04 (blue), and ED04_{MLD} (purple).

In comparison to ED04/ED04_{MLD}, the MEAN particles subduct further north, and to larger amounts in the basins of the Atlantic and Indian Oceans. In MEAN, about 66,9876 of 191,910 particles subduct north of 45°S, compared to 40,749 of 179,765 and 53,376 of 193,460 in ED04 and ED04_{MLD}, respectively. Thus, the northern peak represents 34.1% (MEAN), 21.2% (ED04), and 25.5% (ED04_{MLD}) of volume-weighted particles (Fig. 3.1b). Within the largest zonal peak between 40-110°W, including DP and parts of SA, the share of subducting particles is lower in MEAN with 66.3%, compared to 79.2% (ED04) and 81.0% (ED04_{MLD}). In most other zonal sections, the MEAN experiment shows a larger number of subducting particles compared to ED04/ED04_{MLD}, particularly in the central Atlantic between 40°W and 0° and across the Indian Ocean, extending eastward to New Zealand (60°E to 180°E) (Fig. 3.1b).

Across the ocean basins, particle subduction in MEAN shows a zonally homogeneous patterns. MEAN particle subduction in SA and SI is concentrated north of 40°S throughout the basin, gradually decreasing towards the north. In both basins, the pattern extends to 20°S (Fig. 3.1a), while ED04/ED04_{MLD} show no significant concentrations north of 30°S. In contrast, ED04/ED04_{MLD} particle subduction is not distributed as zonally continuous, as within the SA subduction zone separate patterns emerge in the east and the west. The western pattern is comparable to the zonally homogeneous pattern in MEAN, while the eastern pattern extends southeast towards the SAF. Within SI and SP, ED04/ED04_{MLD} subduction locations show lower concentrations directly north of the SAF, but, in contrast to MEAN, are also found south of the SAF. Within DP, ED04/ED04_{MLD} particle subduction exceeds MEAN particle subduction in the southwest as well as northeast, close to the MCZ (Fig. 3.1c,e). Overall, particle subduction in MEAN is distributed more evenly across ocean basins, whereas ED04/ED04_{MLD} subduction is strongly concentrated around the main subduction zone, the Drake Passage.

ED04_{MLD} and ED04 show large agreement compared to MEAN, but particle subduction in ED04_{MLD} occurs closer to the release area in the South Atlantic and at deeper depths than in ED04 (Fig. 3.1e). In DP, a larger proportion of particles subduct northeast of the Drake Passage, while fewer particles subduct west of it. The SA zone shows more localized subduction, with higher particle concentrations both east and west of the basin, strongly following the South Atlantic Current and the Agulhas Leakage. In SI, subduction shifts westward, with fewer particles subducting south of Australia and New Zealand (Fig. 3.1b). This suggests that the eddy-influenced MLD used in ED04_{MLD} allows particles to make contact with the mixed layer earlier than the MEAN MLD used in ED04.

An indicator of this earlier mixed layer contact in ED04_{MLD} is the distribution of subduction depth, which, in contrast to MEAN and ED04, lacks the bimodality of a shallow and deep subduction regime. Here, the subduction depth is rather normally distributed between 0 and 800m (Fig. 3.1f). This indicates overall deeper mixed layer contact, consistent with deeper local maxima of the MLD (see Fig. 2.4e). For particles with assumed continuous upward motion in the backtracking framework, the deeper mixed layer seems to be reached earlier, which could explain the subduction locations being closer to the release areas. Additionally, the presence of more local maxima in the eddy-influenced mixed layer may explain more concentrated subduction locations, as seen within the Agulhas Leakage (Fig. 3.1e).

The various particle subduction locations mostly overlap with deep winter mixed layers, suggesting strictly seasonal subduction. Further, subduction locations in MEAN are more zonally spread and extend further north, while in ED04/ED04_{MLD}, they are concentrated around the Drake Passage. The eddy-influenced mixed layer of ED04_{MLD} leads to more confined subduction, that is deeper and closer to the release area. Although a greater distance from the release area does not necessarily imply a longer transit time, the differing distributions of subduction locations suggest that transit times will likely vary among the experiments. In addition, eddy effects can influence transit times by either prolonging them, as particles circulate within eddies, or shortening them, due to the higher velocities compared to the mean flow. The next section examines the seasonality of subduction and the transit time distributions of MEAN, ED04, and ED04_{MLD}.

3.2 Transit Times

Subduction in Fig. 3.1 occurs predominantly in regions with deep winter mixed layers, suggesting seasonality in subduction, as these deep mixed layers only exist from July to October (see Fig. 2.4d,f). Considering the time of year when particles subduct confirms this assumption for all experiments (Fig. 3.2a,c,e).

The months in which most particles subduct are September and October in austral spring, while almost no particles subduct between December and May. This is consistent with "Stommel's Demon" (Stommel, 1979) according to which subduction can only be caused by a re-stratification of the mixed layer. The time of subduction is very similar between the experiments, although ED04_{MLD}, implemented with the eddy-influenced mixed layer, shows a wider variance between July and November (Fig. 3.2e). In contrast, the particle transit times from the mixed layer to the AAIW core exhibit significant differences between the experiments.

I display the particle transit time distribution (pTTD) as a histogram with a bin size of 1 year and apply an Inverse Gaussian fit G (details in 2.5), which estimates the mean age Γ (same as for pTTD), width Δ , and relative deviation ϵ (Fig. 3.2b,d,f).

Figure 3.2: Left: Month of subduction for (a) MEAN, (c) ED04, and (e) ED04_{MLD}. Dashed line indicates the average day of year for subduction. Right: particle transit time distribution (pTTD) for (b) MEAN, (d) ED04, and (f) ED04_{MLD}. pTTD bin size is 1 year. Dashed lines describe the Inverse Gaussian fit, with mean age Γ , width Δ , and relative deviation ϵ . Transparent lines show the respective other distributions for comparison.

The pTTDs from all experiments resemble an inverse Gaussian distribution to a first approximation, i.e. a steep peak at low values with a gradually declining tail towards higher values. The peaks are located at transit times of 9 (MEAN), 7 (ED04), and 6 (ED04_{MLD}) years. In the first 20 years, more particles subduct in ED04/ED04_{MLD}, while in the following years, more particles subduct in MEAN (Fig. 3.2b,d,f). The larger proportion of long transit times in MEAN results in a mean age of 31.0 years, which exceeds the mean age of ED04 ($\Gamma=25.0y$) by 6 years and ED04_{MLD} ($\Gamma=22.4y$) by 8.6 years. Additionally, G_{MEAN} shows a larger width of 21.5 years compared to ED04 ($\Delta=19.9y$) and ED04_{MLD} ($\Delta=17.6y$), describing the shift between peak and mean age. The assumption of shorter distances resulting in lower transit times only partly holds. While ED04_{MLD} shows a lower mean age than ED04 with subduction closer to the release area, the MEAN mean age is significantly higher, even though the amount of particles subducting right at the position of particle release is the largest.

The deviation between pTTD and G shows comparable values ($\epsilon_{MEAN} = 3.14 \times 10^{-3}$, $\epsilon_{ED04} = 2.95 \times 10^{-3}$, $\epsilon_{ED04_{MLD}} = 3.03 \times 10^{-3}$) and characteristics among experiments (Fig. 3.2b,d,f). G underestimates the number of particles that enter the AAIW within the first 3-5 years after subduction. Additionally, the decline after the peak does not match the fit accurately. While G overestimates the upper half of the tail, it underestimates the lower half. This deviation between the pTTD and the Inverse Gaussian fit G is particularly evident for pTTD_{MEAN}, where a second peak forms around transit times of 22 years with two-thirds the size of the first peak. This multi-modality does not adhere to the assumption of a single dominant ventilation process. The $\sim 10,000$ additionally subducted particles in ED04_{MLD} compared to ED04 (see Tab. 3.1) show transit times between 1-20 years and reduce the mean age by 2.6 years. A bi-modality in pTTD_{ED04}, significantly weaker than for pTTD_{MEAN}, is thereby further reduced (Fig. 3.2f).

Considering the pTTD of all particles suggests that including eddy effects reduces the estimated AAIW mean age. Deviations from an Inverse Gaussian fit indicate the presence of multiple ventilation processes in the experiments, especially in MEAN, where a multi-modality in pTTD is strongly pronounced. The different subduction zones identified earlier (see Fig. 3.1) support the idea, that AAIW is ventilated from various origins, each with a distinct pathway and transit time. For instance, the DP subduction zone with deep winter mixed layers just upstream of the South Atlantic may provide a faster pathway into the AAIW than the other subduction zones. Thus, fewer particles subducting in the DP zone in MEAN may explain its longer transit times. To better understand the causes for differing transit times, I will now examine the proportion of total particles, transit times, and subduction depth of each subduction zone.

3.3 Subduction Zones

For the comparison between subduction zones, I include DP, SA, and SI. Since fewer than 5% of particles subduct in SP (Fig. 3.3a,f,k), this zone is excluded from further analysis. The DP subduction zone accounts for the largest share of particle subductions throughout the experiments. However, in MEAN, 59.5% of particles subduct in DP, compared to 72.2% in ED04 and 68.5% in ED04_{MLD}, indicating a significantly lower proportion in the former. In contrast, the SI subduction zone contributes a larger share in MEAN (19.9%) compared to ED04 (13.3%) and ED04_{MLD} (11.1%). SA shows an ambivalent distribution, as MEAN (16.3%) and ED04_{MLD} (16.5%) show virtually equal values, significantly higher than ED04 (10.4%). The fraction of particles that reach the mixed layer outside these zones, including in the Pacific Ocean, is small and comparable between the experiments, with 4.4% for MEAN, 4.2% for ED04, and 4.0% for ED04_{MLD} (Fig. 3.3 col.1).

3.3.1 Transit Times

Independent of the experiments, the subduction zones reveal notable differences in pTTD and inverse Gaussian fit G . pTTD_{DP} shows a shape aligning closely with the total pTTD, which accounts for the majority of particles with low transit times (Fig. 3.3 col.2). This proportion reduces for longer transit times, where a discrepancy between pTTD and pTTD_{DP} becomes apparent. pTTD_{SA} and pTTD_{SI} peak later and only show significant influence for transit times larger than 10 years (Fig. 3.3 col.3+4).

In MEAN, pTTD_{DP} includes the majority of particles with transit times lower than 5 years. This proportion sharply decreases for longer transit times, falling below 50% after 20 years. Accordingly, pTTD_{DP} shows a low mean age of 23.4 years (total: 31.0y) (Fig. 3.3b). pTTD_{SA} exhibits a high mean age of 34.9 years, with most transit times larger than 20 years. Notably, pTTD_{SA} shows a low deviation from G_{SA} , resembling an idealized Inverse Gaussian distribution. This indicates a homogeneous subduction process

Figure 3.3: Statistics of the subduction zones DP (blue), SA (orange), SI (green) (see Fig. 3.1). **Column 1:** Proportions for (a) MEAN, (f) ED04, and (k) ED04_{MLD}. **Columns 2-4:** pTTD (solid) and G (dashed) per zone and experiment. Gray line marks total pTTD. **Column 4:** Subduction depths by subduction zone and total (gray) for (e) MEAN, (j) ED04, and (o) ED04_{MLD}.

within SA (Fig. 3.3c). pTTD_{SI} exhibits the highest mean age of 42.8 years and shows a bi-modal structure with peaks at 11 and 26 years (Fig. 3.3d). The width of G_{DP} and G_{SA} is lower than for the total distribution G (21.5y), with respective values of 16.9 years and 13.4 years, while G_{SI} shows a higher width at 23.0 years.

In ED04, pTTD_{DP} represents the majority of transit times, even at longer transit times (Fig. 3.3g). As in MEAN, pTTD_{DP} exhibits the lowest mean age with 21.3 years (total: 21.3y), while pTTD_{SA} and pTTD_{SI} show significantly higher mean ages of 26.7 and 36.1 years, respectively. pTTD_{SA} includes a low amount of transit times resembling pTTD_{DP}, with a minor peak at 7 years, next to the peak at 18 years (Fig. 3.3h). pTTD_{SI} shows a bi-modal structure, which is less pronounced, compared to MEAN (Fig. 3.3i). The widths of G_{DP} and G_{SA} are lower than the total width (19.9y), indicating more isolated ventilation process, while G_{SI} displays a width comparable to the total width.

In alignment with the overall pTTD, the ED04_{MLD} pTTDs of the individual subduction zones show lower mean ages compared to ED04. Notably, the mean age of the SA zone decreases by 5.5 years compared to ED04, while the mean ages of DP and IO reduce by 1.6 and 2.8 years, respectively (Fig. 3.3m). While in ED04, a small fraction of the pTTD_{SA} resembles the pTTD_{DP}, in ED04_{MLD} this fraction dominates the pTTD_{SA}, with a peak at low transit times and a sharp decline afterward.

Separating the pTTD by subduction zones aims to disentangle and isolate individual subduction processes, which are particularly evident in the multi-modal MEAN pTTD. This multi-modality reduces when separating the transit times by subduction zones, as both pTTD_{SA} and pTTD_{SI} are distributed around long transit times and, thus, contribute to a second peak. However, pTTD_{DP} continues to display a multi-

modal distribution, with notable saddle points occurring at 3 and 21 years next to the peak at 9 years (Fig. 3.3b). Particles orbiting the ACC between subduction and entering the AAIW are likely to show an increased transit time, which could contribute to the observed multi-modality. Particles orbiting the ACC indeed show long transit times, but only partly explain the remaining multi-modality in $pTTD_{DP}$ (see appendix C).

In all experiments, $pTTD_{SI}$ shows a large width and two, differently pronounced, peaks around 10 and 25 years. As the chosen area for SI is the largest and subduction locations are widely distributed, a large width is plausible. The bi-modality, however, might also indicate two separate pathways, slow and fast, which might explain the large differences in $pTTD_{SI}$ mean age throughout the experiments. As transit times seem to be related to subduction depths, the next section presents these, separated by subduction zones.

3.3.2 Depth Distribution

The distribution of subduction depth shows a clear influence of the different subduction zones. In DP, subduction occurs in a wide range of depths from 100 to 800m, while in the SA, subduction is concentrated predominantly in the upper 300m. In the SI, particles subduct in depths between 0-600m (Fig. 3.3 col.4).

These characteristic subduction depths for each zone strongly influence each experiment's subduction depth distribution. For instance, subduction in the upper 200m is more pronounced for the MEAN experiment, due to the higher proportion of SA particles. However, the differences between ED04 and MEAN are not limited to the relative contribution of zones; the subduction depth in DP is by about 100m deeper in MEAN, whereas the SI zone shows a peak in the upper 100m, which is absent in ED04. This may further indicate the presence of a secondary pathway originating from SI, which is strongly pronounced in MEAN. These differences create the bi-modal structure in the MEAN subduction depth distribution, a feature that is less pronounced in ED04 (Fig. 3.3e,j).

In contrast to MEAN and ED04, the ED04_{MLD} subduction depth does not exhibit a distinct bi-modal structure. While the subduction depth distribution in the DP zone is comparable to MEAN, the SI zone shows an increase in subduction below 300m. In the SA zone, the prominent shallow subduction depth deepens by around 100m, and subduction at depths greater than 400m becomes apparent (Fig. 3.3o).

The subduction depth is strongly influenced by the MLD, as it determines the depth to which particles are tracked. When analyzing the subduction depths, two distinct subduction regimes emerge: deep subduction, which is localized and likely driven by lateral advection from seasonal MLD extremes, and shallow subduction, which occurs at lower depths and seems less dependent on local maxima. The representation of the mixed layer is crucial in this context, as implementing the eddy-influenced MLD shows an increase in deep subduction within the SA zone. This causes a reduction in SA mean age, suggesting that particles subducting within DP and SI in ED04 and MEAN, may in ED04_{MLD} subduct in SA, closer to the release area. This is particularly evident near the ARZ and the MCZ, where localized maxima in the MLD appear to drive this shift.

Considering particles at the time of subduction indicates differing advective processes between the MEAN and ED04/ED04_{MLD} experiments. To explain these differences in characteristics and relative distribution, I will analyze the trajectories and velocities of the particles. Specifically, I aim to investigate, why a greater proportion of particles in the MEAN experiment subducts within SA and SI, and why these zones

are associated with longer transit times. Furthermore, I will explore the overall longer transit times observed in the MEAN experiment, that are seemingly independent of the specific subduction zones. Before considering the spatial routes of the pathways, I consider the diapycnal component of each subduction zone, estimating which of the pathways expands along isopycnals, and which relies on diabatic mixing.

3.4 Diapycnal Component

To estimate the diapycnal component of the ventilation pathways, I consider the density deviation $\Delta\sigma_0$, as described in section 2.6, and plot the water mass properties at the time of subduction. $\Delta\sigma_0$ shows significant differences between the pathways of the individual subduction zones. While $\Delta\sigma_{0,DP}$ is small in all experiments ($\sim 0.28\text{kg/m}^3$), $\Delta\sigma_{0,SA}$ and $\Delta\sigma_{0,SI}$ range between 0.73 and 1.19kg/m^3 and are especially large in MEAN (Fig. 3.4a).

Remarkably, only DP and low amounts of SA particles for ED04/ED04_{MLD} maintain densities within the AAIW density criterion, while the density of particles when subducting in SI (around 26.5kg/m^3) and SA (around 26.0kg/m^3) is significantly reduced (Fig. 3.4a,c,e). Due to larger values for $\Delta\sigma_{0,SA}$ and $\Delta\sigma_{0,SI}$, combined with the stronger contribution of those subduction zones, MEAN particles exhibit an overall larger density deviation (0.60kg/m^3) than ED04 and ED04_{MLD} (0.42kg/m^3).

The water mass properties differ between the subduction zones. DP particles constitute cold ($0\text{-}8^\circ\text{C}$) and fresh ($34.0\text{-}34.5\text{g/kg}$) water masses, while SI particles exhibit temperatures between $6\text{-}15^\circ\text{C}$ and a salinity range of $34.5\text{-}35.5\text{g/kg}$. Particles subducting within SA show a wide range of properties, with a fraction resembling the DP water mass properties, while others show warm ($15\text{-}17^\circ\text{C}$) and haline ($35.0\text{-}36.0\text{g/kg}$) properties (Fig. 3.4b,d,f). Discrepancies between MEAN and ED04/ED04_{MLD} become apparent for SA and SI, as in MEAN, particles within those zones exhibit temperatures above 20°C and surpass the 26kg/m^3 density contour.

Figure 3.4: Density at subduction location for (a) MEAN, (c) ED04, and (e) ED04_{MLD}. Numbers in the legend represent $\Delta\sigma_0$. (b,d,f) T-S diagram and σ_0 contours for each experiment. Red dashed lines and contours show the AAIW density definition. All plots separated by subduction zones DP (blue), SA (orange), SI (green).

3.5 Ventilation Pathways

To investigate the ventilation pathways of AAIW, I analyze the particle trajectories between subduction location and AAIW. I utilize a $2 \times 2^\circ$ grid to visualize the pathways, marking grid cells that each particle traverses at least once. The number of particles that pass through a grid cell divided by the total number of particles released yields a particle probability per grid cell (\mathcal{P}). As the particles are released in the South Atlantic, \mathcal{P} is highest in this region and diminishes with distance from the release area. When passing a subduction zone, where particle trajectories end, \mathcal{P} reduces further. As ED04 and ED04_{MLD} trajectories only differ by the subduction criterion, I use ED04_{MLD} for further comparison to MEAN, including decomposition effects on both flow and mixed layer representation. I present and discuss \mathcal{P} for MEAN and ED04_{MLD}, and their difference MEAN-ED04_{MLD}, on a logarithmic scale.

Both experiments exhibit \mathcal{P}_{max} in the western South Atlantic, particularly around the MCZ. This maximum extends into the South Atlantic Current and connects to the SAF at approximately 50°S , with $\mathcal{P} \geq 10^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. A secondary pathway links the South Atlantic to the Indian Ocean via the Agulhas Leakage, with $\mathcal{P} \sim 10^{-1}$. The Indian subtropical gyre shows a moderate particle probability of $10^{-2} \leq \mathcal{P} \leq 10^{-1}$, primarily at the western boundary, where the narrow Agulhas Current and Mozambique Channel concentrate the particle trajectories. A similar pattern shows in the Pacific basin, though with lower particle probabilities of $10^{-3} \leq \mathcal{P} \leq 10^{-2}$. In the ACC, a consistent probability of about $10^{-\frac{3}{2}} \leq \mathcal{P} \leq 10^{-1}$ prevails, indicating that approximately 1 in 10 particles orbit the ACC before entering the Atlantic AAIW (Fig. 3.5).

Figure 3.5: Particle probability \mathcal{P} of all subducted particles on a $2 \times 2^\circ$ grid for (a) ED04_{MLD}, (b) MEAN, and (c) the difference MEAN-ED04_{MLD}. Color indication is logarithmic, with steps of 0.5. For the difference (c), an excess of ED04_{MLD} particle probability is blue and an excess of MEAN particle probability is red. Red/black lines mark the position of the SAF and PF.

The pathways determined in ED04_{MLD} and MEAN differ significantly, particularly in the western boundary currents, the South Atlantic’s connection to the ACC, and the track of the ACC itself. $\mathcal{P}(\text{MEAN})$ exceeds $\mathcal{P}(\text{ED04}_{MLD})$ in all western boundary currents between 20 and 40°S. In the South Atlantic, one-third of MEAN trajectories traverse the Brazil Current and the main pathway towards the Indian Ocean extends northeast into the Mozambique Channel. In consequence, also the particle probability in the Indian Ocean basin increases by $\Delta\mathcal{P} \sim 10^{-2}$ in the MEAN experiment. The western boundary current in the Pacific Ocean shows a similar increase in particle probability compared to the ED04_{MLD} experiment, which is sustained throughout the path of the subtropical gyre.

The ED04_{MLD} experiment, in contrast, reveals a higher \mathcal{P} in the South Atlantic outside the Brazil Current. Notably, at the edge of the SAF, $\mathcal{P}(\text{ED04}_{MLD})$ exceeds $\mathcal{P}(\text{MEAN})$ by $\Delta\mathcal{P} \sim 10^{-1}$, indicating an additional 19,000 particles passing through this region. The particle probabilities in the ARZ differ markedly between the two experiments: while $\mathcal{P}(\text{ED04}_{MLD})$ dominates the area southwest of the Cape of Good Hope, $\mathcal{P}(\text{MEAN})$ is highest toward the Mozambique Channel in the northeast. Along the Atlantic SAF up to the Drake Passage, $\mathcal{P}(\text{ED04}_{MLD})$ remains higher than $\mathcal{P}(\text{MEAN})$, suggesting a different effect of the ARZ on particle advection in the two experiments.

Along the ACC track, the MEAN experiment exhibits a higher ($\Delta\mathcal{P} \sim 10^{-1}$) particle probability, while the ED04_{MLD} shows greater probabilities ($\Delta\mathcal{P} \sim 10^{-2}$) south of the SAF. This observation indicates that particles in the MEAN experiment tend to follow the jets of the ACC more closely, possibly resulting in a greater number of particles orbiting the ACC (see section 3.3.1). Additionally, the zonal ACC fronts may constitute a barrier for the meridional movement of MEAN particles, which the ED04_{MLD} particles can overcome more easily.

Considering these pathways, I identify two key regions where the absence of eddy effects significantly influences particle advection. The first is the MCZ at 50°W, which seems to mark a junction along the SAF. Here, a considerable proportion of the MEAN particles diverges northward toward the Brazil Current, while most ED04_{MLD} particles cross the SAF, heading south into the Drake Passage. MEAN particles, heading towards the Drake Passage avoid crossing the SAF, and instead traverse along a narrow section between the SAF and the South American continent. The second key region is the ARZ at 20°E. The pathways in the ED04_{MLD} experiment indicate a return flow from the Atlantic to the southwest into the ACC, whereas the MEAN trajectories favor a transition to the Indian Ocean via the Agulhas Current (Fig. 3.5c).

To determine how these key regions influence the ventilation pathways, I consider the pathways individually for each subduction zone. This allows to determine the routes taken by the particles from the subduction zone to the AAIW, potentially explaining the differing transit times for each zone.

3.5.1 Pathways by Subduction Zones

The ventilation pathways of each subduction zone show a unique pattern, that allows to estimate their sensitivity to eddy effects. With the ARZ and MCZ identified as key regions for eddy effects, all but particles subducting in SA have to cross these regions.

The pathways of the DP are concentrated in the western South Atlantic. The direct pathway via the MCZ shows the largest particle probability, with $\mathcal{P} \sim 10^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, but pathways along the SAF, entering the AAIW via the central and eastern South Atlantic are also recognizable, especially in ED04_{MLD} (Fig. 3.6d). For DP, a pathway orbiting the ACC before entering the AAIW plays a moderate role, with $\mathcal{P} \sim 10^{-\frac{3}{2}}$. Considering

Figure 3.6: \mathcal{P} by subduction zone relative to all particle trajectories. (a,d,g) DP, (b,e,h) SA, (c,f,i) SI. Each column like Fig. 3.5.

the differences between MEAN and $ED04_{MLD}$, a $\mathcal{P}(ED04_{MLD})$ is higher over the entire domain, which is explainable by the larger proportion of $ED04_{MLD}$ particles subducting in DP. However, $\mathcal{P}(\text{MEAN})$ shows partially higher values just north of the SAF, especially within the Drake Passage (Fig. 3.6g).

For SA, the majority of the particles remain in the South Atlantic and circulate predominantly in the subtropical gyre between 20-40°S (Fig. 3.6b). MEAN trajectories are concentrated on the western boundary north of the MCZ, while $ED04_{MLD}$ trajectories are also found in the eastern margin, close to the ARZ (Fig. 3.6e). The pattern of $\mathcal{P}(ED04_{MLD})$ suggests that particles are deflected at the ARZ and less probable to leave the South Atlantic towards the Indian Ocean. Pathways leaving the South Atlantic, before entering into the AAIW, exist mainly for MEAN particles orbiting the ACC.

The ventilation pathways of the SI subduction zone show a complex pattern for both experiments. Apparently, two fundamentally different pathways exist in equal proportions (Fig. 3.6c). On the one hand, particles from SI can reach the AAIW via the ACC track through the Drake Passage; on the other hand, there exists a pathway passing through the basin of the Indian Ocean and, via the Agulhas Leakage, into the South Atlantic. Even though more MEAN particles subduct within SA, both pathways also exist in $ED04_{MLD}$ (Fig. 3.6f). $\mathcal{P}(ED04_{MLD})$ is higher south of the ARZ and at the eastern boundary of the South Atlantic, but significantly lower within the track of the Agulhas Leakage. This indicates a stronger transport through the Agulhas Leakage in the absence of eddies (Fig. 3.6i). Further, $\mathcal{P}(\text{MEAN})$ is higher along the Malvinas Current and the ACC, as well as in the entire Indian Ocean, including the Agulhas Current and Mozambique Channel.

Across the different subduction zones, $\mathcal{P}(ED04_{MLD})$ maintains higher values south of both identified key regions, the ARZ and MCZ, as well as south of the SAF (Fig. 3.6g,h,i). Considering particle velocities within those regions can clarify, how eddy effects cause deflection along the ARZ or facilitate the crossing of the SAF. While these key regions may determine the distribution in subduction zones, the overall longer transit times of the MEAN particles may be explained by lower velocities. In the following I consider particle velocities along meridional sections of these two key regions and particle velocities at the depth of 400m, which represents the upper extent of the AAIW.

3.6 Particle Velocities

I calculate the particle velocity using a three-dimensional grid with $2^\circ \times 2^\circ \times 50\text{m}$ spacing. For each grid cell and particle, I compute the average three-dimensional velocity over all time steps, provided the particle is located within that grid cell at one or more time steps. I analyze the particle velocities along one depth level (400-500m depth, Fig. 3.7) and at the MCZ and ARZ along a meridional section averaged over 10 degrees of longitude ($45\text{-}55^\circ\text{W}$ and $15\text{-}25^\circ\text{E}$, Fig. 3.8). For visualization of the three-dimensional velocities, I use color coding for normal velocities and arrows for lateral velocities. To avoid single outlier particle velocities to represent a grid cell, I only include grid cells where more than 100 particles contribute velocities. For each section, I assess the mean velocities of both ED04_{MLD} and MEAN, and their difference $\text{ED04}_{MLD} - \text{MEAN}$. This difference reflects the eddy contribution to the total velocity field.

Figure 3.7: Mean particle velocity for (a) MEAN and (b) ED04_{MLD} between 400-500m depth on a $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ grid. Lateral velocities are indicated by arrows, vertical velocity by color. (c) Difference (eddy contribution) $\text{ED04}_{MLD} - \text{MEAN}$. Grid points with less than 100 particles contributing are excluded. Red lines mark the position of the SAF and PF. Gray boxed indicate meridional sections (MCZ,ARZ) shown in Fig. 3.8.

The horizontal particle velocities at depths of 400-500m depth illustrate the zonal track of the ACC at $50\text{-}60^\circ\text{S}$, along with a meridional component east of the Drake Passage. In the South Atlantic, north of the SAF, movement towards the northeast is visible, which is more pronounced in ED04_{MLD} than in MEAN. Other horizontal velocities are relatively low in comparison, with the exception of those in the Indian Ocean subtropical gyre (Fig. 3.7a+b). Vertical velocities, indicated by the color coding, show downwelling in both experiments although this downwelling is generally stronger in ED04_{MLD} . Along the primary pathways into the South Atlantic, entering from the Drake Passage and through the Agulhas Leakage, the vertical velocities in ED04_{MLD} reach about 10^{-6}m/s , compared to about $0.5 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{m/s}$ in

MEAN (Fig. 3.7a+b). Examining the differences between the two experiments shows that the eddy contribution often opposes the horizontal MEAN velocities. This is particularly the case in the Atlantic section of the ACC and northwest of the ARZ, where the eddy contribution almost completely counteracts the zonal motion of the MEAN experiment (Fig. 3.7c).

Figure 3.8: Mean particle velocity at (a,c,e) MCZ and (b,d,f) ARZ for (a,b) MEAN and (c,d) ED04_{MLD} along a meridional section on a 2°x50m grid. Meridional and vertical velocities are indicated by arrows, zonal velocity by color. (e,f) Difference ED04_{MLD}-MEAN. Grid points with less than 100 particles contributing are excluded. Yellow bars mark the positions of SAF and PF.

In the MCZ along 45-55°W, the particle velocity direction is largely homogeneous. South of 35°S, the primary movement is eastward, equatorward, and downward (Fig. 3.8a,c). In ED04_{MLD}, the zonal velocity gradually increases with latitude, peaking at 0.02 m/s between 50-60°S (Fig. 3.8c). In contrast, the MEAN experiment exhibits a steep meridional gradient in the zonal velocity at 45°S and 55°S, with velocities of 0.02m/s already present between 45-50°S, and exceeding 0.05m/s south of 55°S (Fig. 3.8a). For the meridional and vertical velocities, an equatorward downwelling is evident, reaching its maximum at depths of 250-500m between 35-50°S. This meridional downwelling occurs in both experiments but is stronger in the ED04_{MLD} experiment. Moreover, a slight poleward downwelling is evident close to the surface north of 35°S, which is stronger pronounced in the MEAN experiment. The eddy contribution has two notable effects here. Firstly, the zonal eddy contribution south of 45°S counteracts the zonal ACC, reducing the meridional gradient of the MEAN velocity. Secondly, the eddy contribution causes an equatorward meridional velocity across all latitudes, especially between 35 and 40°S and south of 50°S (Fig. 3.8e).

In the ARZ between 15-25°E, positive zonal velocities indicate the presence of the ACC at latitudes of 45-50°S. The Agulhas Current between 30 and 40°S exhibits negative zonal velocities. Similar to the MCZ, the MEAN experiment shows a strong meridional gradient in the zonal velocities of the ACC, which is less pronounced in ED04_{MLD} (Fig. 3.8b,c). Furthermore, in ED04_{MLD} the Agulhas Current is detectable only to a depth of 500m, whereas in the MEAN experiment, it appears more barotropic, showing negative zonal velocities down to 700m (Fig. 3.8b). The meridional and vertical velocities show large differences between the two experiments. The ED04_{MLD} experiment shows equatorward downwelling over the entire section, similar to what is observed in the MCZ. This downwelling is strongest between 40-50°S down to a depth of 750m. In contrast, the MEAN experiment exhibits only very weak meridional and vertical velocities. Although these velocities also indicate equatorward downwelling outside the Agulhas Current, a poleward downwelling is present within the Agulhas Current (Fig. 3.8b). The eddy contribution in this section primarily has zonal and meridional effects. In the Agulhas Current, it opposes the zonal mean velocities, effectively counteracting the Agulhas Current below a depth of 500m. Within the ACC, the eddy contribution reduces the strong gradient of the zonal velocities. This is connected to the meridional movement, where the eddy contribution adds a consistent equatorward motion, facilitating crossing from the ACC into the ocean basin (Fig. 3.8f).

4 Summary and Discussion

Summary of results:

- Including eddies into the flow field increases the contribution of Drake Passage water masses to the South Atlantic AAIW from 60% to 72%, reducing contributions from more northern subduction zones. Eddies shift subduction southward, resulting in colder and fresher source waters. The MCZ gains importance as a source region with the eddy-influenced MLD representation (Fig. 3.1).
- Eddy effects reduce the estimated mean age of AAIW from 31.0 to 22.4 years. Of the 8.6-year reduction, 1.4 years are attributed to increased Drake Passage water masses, which exhibit low transit times. 2.6 years are attributed to deeper subduction near the AAIW core, due to the eddy-influenced MLD. The remaining 4.6 years are related to faster advection, as eddies contribute two-thirds of total kinetic energy (Fig. 3.2+3.3).
- Eddy effects slightly reduce the overall pTTD width, representing diffusivity along pathways. When considering the pTTD for subduction zones separately, an ambiguous picture emerges. Resolving eddy velocities does not seem to have a clear effect on the diffusivity along ventilation pathways (Fig. 3.2+3.3).
- Eddy effects maintain isopycnal ventilation, as pathways for Drake Passage water masses are mostly isopycnal, while northward subduction zones exhibit reduced density compared to the AAIW core. The diapycnal component in those pathways is more pronounced in the mean flow field (Fig. 3.4).
- Eddy effects reduce mean flow transports in the Brazil Current and the Mozambique Channel. Resolving distinct Agulhas rings reduces transport through the Agulhas Leakage, limiting exchange with the Indian Ocean. As a result, eddy effects reduce transport along pathways that extend across subtropical gyres (Fig. 3.6).
- Eddies facilitate the crossing of barriers like the SAF, which allows water masses to separate from the ACC. Without overcoming ACC fronts, pathways of Drake Passage waters are bound to the continental margin of South America (Fig. 3.5+3.8).
- Within the eddy-rich MCZ and ARZ, eddies accelerate downwelling in the upper AAIW depth range, likely contributing to shorter transit times (Fig. 3.7).

Subduction Zones The spatial distribution of particle subduction aligns with previous studies, particularly Sallée et al. (2012), which identifies an important role of the Drake Passage for the ventilation of the pycnocline. The study confirms that eddy fluxes limit subduction north of the SAF, which is mostly Ekman driven. Subduction in the Drake Passage is mostly driven by lateral advection, which aligns with the strictly seasonal and deep subduction identified here.

A Lagrangian study by Tamsitt et al. (2017), identifying upwelling of deep waters within the ACC, further demonstrates the importance of the Drake Passage for Southern Ocean water mass formation. In the Drake Passage, a significant fraction of particles reaches the ocean interior, likely transitioning into AAIW. Assuming minor diapycnal movement in this thesis, particles that did not reach the mixed layer may directly originate from the deep water along the upwelling zones identified in Tamsitt et al. (2017).

Similarly to the Drake Passage and the more northern subduction zones identified here, a Lagrangian backtracking study by Chouksey et al. (2022) finds a bimodal meridional distribution for particle subduction. The study suggests subduction distributed along the ACC, using surface contact instead of mixed

layer crossing to identify subduction. Applying this surface criterion to the eddy-mean flow experiments of this thesis reveals an intensified northward shift of subduction without eddy effects (see appendix [B](#)).

Mean age and diffusivity Previous studies estimate South Atlantic AAIW mean ages between 20-40 years (D. W. Waugh et al., [2019](#)), with lower mean ages of about 20 years in the upper layer of the AAIW (Fine et al., [2017](#)). Therefore, the mean ages determined in this thesis (23-31 years) are plausible, as the estimated mean ages reflect the whole depth range between 400 and 1200 m. As with previous research, mean ages vary between source regions, with Drake Passage waters showing short, and South Atlantic and Indian Ocean waters long mean ages (Chouksey et al., [2022](#)). The difference between mean ages by source region is significantly larger in this thesis, presumably as here the estimation of subduction includes the local MLD, which further reduces the mean age of Drake Passage waters.

The source regions show characteristic diffusivities along their pathways, which align with Chouksey et al. ([2022](#)), as routes of Drake Passage and South Atlantic waters show low, and Indian Ocean waters high diffusivity. However, the South Indian Ocean subduction zone covers a large area and presumably multiple pathways towards the South Atlantic AAIW, which in part defies the estimation as a one-dimensional advection-diffusion process. Against the general assumption, ventilation pathways in the mean flow do not exhibit decreased diffusivity compared to the eddying flow. Since the mean flow is derived from the eddying model output, a possible eddy-induced diffusivity may still be present in it.

Pathways The ventilation pathways identified here align with those described by a tracer advection study by Jones et al. ([2016](#)). This study also highlights the importance of the MCZ as source region, which in this thesis shows when including both eddying flow and eddy-influenced MLD representation. Further, a Lagrangian particle study by McAufield ([2019](#)) finds multiple pathways connecting the Drake Passage with the South Atlantic AAIW along the SAF. These pathways show when eddy effects are included, but are strongly reduced in the mean flow.

The different influence of pathways originating in the South Indian Ocean between eddy and mean flow also appears to be evident between high and low model resolution. While studies on rather coarse-resolution models (Speich et al., [2001](#); Drijfhout and De Ruijter, [2005](#)) identify this pathway as decisive for central Atlantic AAIW, those on high-resolution models show a reduced influence of this ‘warm route’ (Rühs et al., [2019](#)).

The pathway connecting the South Atlantic mixed layers with its intermediate water shows a strong diapycnal component in this thesis. This pathway is also described in a study by Chouksey et al. ([2022](#)), which uses the identical model. This pathway is likely caused by spurious mixing velocities in the POP model. These rather slow velocities may explain long transit times despite the short distances traveled. Evidence for this route is given by observed (Li et al., [2022](#)) and modeled (Calil, [2017](#)) subduction of lighter water masses within the South Atlantic, which might diabatically enter the AAIW. The diapycnal South Atlantic pathway is stronger pronounced in the absence of eddies, which otherwise may displace the water masses faster along isopycnals.

Particle velocities A study by Rimaud et al. ([2012](#)) shows that lateral transport and overturning in the ARZ are closely linked to the formation of Agulhas rings. In this thesis, particle velocities show an eddy contribution within the ARZ, which reduces zonal mean velocities and enhances northward downwelling. This integrates a larger proportion of ACC water masses into the rings, whereas without eddies the Agulhas Leakage is nourished almost exclusively by Indian Ocean water masses. The reduced

transports across the SAF in the mean flow also show in similar decomposition studies, which release particles (McAufield, 2019) and tracers (Kamenkovich et al., 2017) within the ACC. The tracer study, in alignment with this thesis, connects the reduced meridional transport with longer mean ages.

Limitations The definition of the mean used in this thesis, a 10-year mean for each day of the year, stems from the assumption of a seasonal cycle in the flow field and MLD, relevant for AAIW ventilation. While this is the case for the MLD, variability of the flow field within the Southern Ocean does not seem to follow a strong seasonal cycle (see Fig. 2.2). Although ACC strength and MCZ position are subject to seasonal variability (Gan et al., 1998; Matano et al., 1993), these are unlikely to affect dynamics below 400 meters. To estimate the effect of maintaining a seasonal cycle, one could deploy the particle tracking algorithm on constant mean flow. This might further isolate eddy effects from the mean but be limited regarding the MLD representation. However, the definition of the mean defined here separates the mesoscale eddies enough to adequately address the research questions raised.

For the eddying velocity field, it is necessary to determine whether the selection of a single year (2004) is representative, or merely representing annual variability. A comparison with the year 2005, which exhibits the largest difference in KE to 2004 within the decade, shows indisputable similarity regarding AAIW ventilation (see appendix A). As for lower KE, the results obtained from the 2005 model output should be closer to those of the MEAN state, as the deviation from MKE, i.e. the eddy effects, are smaller. In fact, a minor increase in transit times and a stronger contribution of Indian Ocean waters is evident, but too small to be considered robust.

The repeated year setup also limits the estimation of AAIW ventilation. As the time scales of ventilation are significantly longer than one year, the estimated transit times and pathways are only affected by limited variability. This is in contrast to actual ventilation processes, which are influenced by varying dynamics over decades. Further, fields in the repeated year setup show a discontinuity between December 31st and January 1st, which can result in diabatic displacement of particles. In the mean flow, as averaged over 10 consecutive years, the discontinuity should be insignificant. However, pathways of the eddying flow experiment show lower diapycnal components than for mean flow, so it is unlikely that the discontinuity causes significant diapycnal displacement. Other Lagrangian tracking experiments show comparable (Olivé Abelló, 2023), but also significantly lower (McAufield, 2019) diapycnal components along trajectories, depending on the spatial and temporal scales of particle tracking.

The subduction criterion in this study, based on reaching the MLD, could be improved. In this Lagrangian backtracking study, I assume that particles reaching the mixed layer are immediately in equilibrium with the surface, but this is unlikely for deep mixed layers. However, tracking within the mixed layer is not accurate, as mixed layer dynamics are parameterized in the POP model and thus not present in model output velocities. Distinguishing between particles that remain in the mixed layer and particles just briefly touching it, might improve estimates of subduction for particle backtracking.

5 Conclusions and Prospects

This thesis identifies the effects of mesoscale eddies on the ventilation of the South Atlantic AAIW with Lagrangian backtracking based on an eddy-mean flow decomposition performed on model output of the 1/10° POP ocean model, highlighting impacts on sources of origin, mean age, and pathways.

The northward-shifted AAIW origin and increased age estimates without resolved eddy motion can help to evaluate inaccuracies in coarse models that rely on parameterizations for representing eddy effects. Derived from this thesis, such inaccuracies can include an underestimation of carbon uptake and meridional heat transport, which would be especially impactful in climate projections. Estimating to which extent coarse resolution models are comparable with the mean flow created in this thesis, and how parameterizations succeed in reproducing the identified eddy effects, are tasks for future studies.

The Malvinas Confluence and Agulhas Retroflexion Zones show to be highly influential in directing ventilation pathways, with eddies strongly affecting meridional and vertical motion. The importance of both regions identified here underlines the relevance of studying their dynamics in detail, and further raises the question of which mechanisms and junctures regulate the ventilation of the Pacific and Indian Ocean pycnocline.

This thesis relates eddy effects with the reduction of mean age, i.e. increased ventilation rates and carbon uptake. An increase in eddy activity would consequently imply a further reduction in mean age, alongside a strengthened contribution of Drake Passage waters. Future trends, including an intensification and poleward shift of the westerlies, will likely increase not only eddy activity but also the mean flow. Estimating how ventilation processes will change under increased atmospheric forcing, and whether an increase of ventilation rates due to eddy effects is limited, is another possible avenue of investigation.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank Carsten Eden for educating me as an oceanographer and encouraging a questioning attitude. I thank Alexa Griesel for thorough supervision and valuable suggestions from approach to realization. I also thank Manita Chouksey for providing the foundation of the research topic and for motivating me to be committed, especially in the writing process. Thank you Silvano and Che for long years of company in the field of oceanography, for on- and off-topic talks, and for technical solutions of all kinds. Thank you Paulina, Luca, Paul, and Maged for emotional, logistic and nutritious support.

References

- Andrews, D., & McIntyre, M. E. (1976). Planetary waves in horizontal and vertical shear: The generalized Eliassen-Palm relation and the mean zonal acceleration. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 33(11), 2031–2048.
- Balwada, D., Speer, K. G., LaCasce, J. H., Owens, W. B., Marshall, J., & Ferrari, R. (2016). Circulation and stirring in the southeast Pacific Ocean and the Scotia Sea sectors of the Antarctic circumpolar current. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 46(7), 2005–2027.
- Bennett, S. L. (1988). *Where three oceans meet: The Agulhas retroflection region* [Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology].
- Calil, P. H. (2017). Wind-induced subduction at the South Atlantic subtropical front. *Ocean Dynamics*, 67(10), 1351–1365.
- Chelton, D. B., DeSzoeke, R. A., Schlax, M. G., El Naggar, K., & Siwertz, N. (1998). Geographical variability of the first baroclinic Rossby radius of deformation. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 28(3), 433–460.
- Chouksey, M., Griesel, A., Eden, C., & Steinfeldt, R. (2022). Transit time distributions and ventilation pathways using CFCs and Lagrangian backtracking in the South Atlantic of an eddying ocean model. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 52(7), 1531–1548.
- Delandmeter, P., & Van Sebille, E. (2019). The parcels v2.0 Lagrangian framework: New field interpolation schemes. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(8), 3571–3584.
- Drijfhout, S., & De Ruijter, W. (2005). The origin of intermediate and subpolar mode waters crossing the Atlantic equator in OCCAM. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32(6).
- Eden, C. (2007). Eddy length scales in the North Atlantic Ocean. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 112(C6).
- Farneti, R., Delworth, T. L., Rosati, A. J., Griffies, S. M., & Zeng, F. (2010). The role of mesoscale eddies in the rectification of the Southern Ocean response to climate change. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 40(7), 1539–1557.
- Fine, R. A., Peacock, S., Maltrud, M. E., & Bryan, F. O. (2017). A new look at ocean ventilation time scales and their uncertainties. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 122(5), 3771–3798.
- Gan, J., Mysak, L. A., & Straub, D. N. (1998). Simulation of the South Atlantic Ocean circulation and its seasonal variability. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 103(C5), 10241–10251.
- Gent, P. R., & McWilliams, J. C. (1990). Isopycnal mixing in ocean circulation models. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 20(1), 150–155.
- Gordon, A. L. (1989). Brazil-Malvinas confluence—1984. *Deep Sea Research Part A: Oceanographic Research Papers*, 36(3), 359–384.
- Gouretski, V. (2018). Woce-Argo global hydrographic climatology (WAGHC version 1.0). https://doi.org/10.1594/WDCC/WAGHC_V1.0
- Hogg, A. M., Meredith, M. P., Chambers, D. P., Abrahamsen, E. P., Hughes, C. W., & Morrison, A. K. (2015). Recent trends in the Southern Ocean eddy field. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 120(1), 257–267.
- Ingmanson, D. E., & Wallace, W. J. (1995). *Oceanography: an introduction (5th edition)*. Wadsworth.
- Jones, D. C., Meijers, A. J., Shuckburgh, E., Sallée, J.-B., Haynes, P., McAufield, E. K., & Mazloff, M. R. (2016). How does the subantarctic mode water ventilate the Southern Hemisphere subtropics? *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 121(9), 6558–6582.
- Kamenkovich, I., Garraffo, Z., Pennel, R., & Fine, R. A. (2017). Importance of mesoscale eddies and mean circulation in ventilation of the Southern Ocean. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 122(4), 2724–2741.

- Katsumata, K., Sloyan, B., & Masuda, S. (2013). Diapycnal and isopycnal transports in the southern ocean estimated by a box inverse model. *Journal of physical oceanography*, 43(11), 2270–2287.
- Khatiwala, S., Primeau, F., & Hall, T. (2009). Reconstruction of the history of anthropogenic CO₂ concentrations in the ocean. *Nature*, 462(7271), 346–349.
- Large, W., Danabasoglu, G., Doney, S. C., & McWilliams, J. C. (1997). Sensitivity to surface forcing and boundary layer mixing in a global ocean model: Annual-mean climatology. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 27(11), 2418–2447.
- Large, W., McWilliams, J. C., & Doney, S. C. (1994). Oceanic vertical mixing: A review and a model with a nonlocal boundary layer parameterization. *Reviews of geophysics*, 32(4), 363–403.
- Large, W., & Yeager, S. G. (2004). Diurnal to decadal global forcing for ocean and sea-ice models: The data sets and flux climatologies.
- Large, W., & Yeager, S. (2009). The global climatology of an interannually varying air–sea flux data set. *Climate dynamics*, 33, 341–364.
- Li, Z., Groeskamp, S., Cerovečki, I., & England, M. H. (2022). The origin and fate of antarctic intermediate water in the southern ocean. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 52(11), 2873–2890.
- Macdonald, A. M., & Wunsch, C. (1996). An estimate of global ocean circulation and heat fluxes. *Nature*, 382(6590), 436–439.
- Maltrud, M., Bryan, F., & Peacock, S. (2010). Boundary impulse response functions in a century-long eddying global ocean simulation. *Environmental fluid mechanics*, 10, 275–295.
- Matano, R. P., Schlax, M. G., & Chelton, D. B. (1993). Seasonal variability in the southwestern atlantic. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 98(C10), 18027–18035.
- McAulfield, E. K. (2019). *Lagrangian study of the southern ocean circulation* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Cambridge].
- Moreton, S. M., Ferreira, D., Roberts, M. J., & Hewitt, H. T. (2020). Evaluating surface eddy properties in coupled climate simulations with ‘eddy-present’ and ‘eddy-rich’ ocean resolution. *Ocean Modelling*, 147, 101567.
- Morrison, A. K., Waugh, D. W., Hogg, A. M., Jones, D. C., & Abernathy, R. P. (2022). Ventilation of the southern ocean pycnocline. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, 14(1), 405–430.
- Olivé Abelló, A. (2023). *Transformations and pathways of southern ocean waters into the south atlantic ocean* [Doctoral dissertation, Universitat de Barcelona].
- Redi, M. H. (1982). Oceanic isopycnal mixing by coordinate rotation. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 12(10), 1154–1158.
- Rimaud, J., Speich, S., Blanke, B., & Grima, N. (2012). The exchange of intermediate water in the south-east atlantic: Water mass transformations diagnosed from the lagrangian analysis of a regional ocean model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 117(C8).
- Rühs, S., Schwarzkopf, F. U., Speich, S., & Biastoch, A. (2019). Cold vs. warm water route–sources for the upper limb of the atlantic meridional overturning circulation revisited in a high-resolution ocean model. *Ocean Science*, 15(3), 489–512.
- Sallée, J.-B., Matear, R. J., Rintoul, S. R., & Lenton, A. (2012). Localized subduction of anthropogenic carbon dioxide in the southern hemisphere oceans. *Nature Geoscience*, 5(8), 579–584.
- Sallée, J.-B., Speer, K., Rintoul, S., & Wijffels, S. (2010). Southern ocean thermocline ventilation. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 40(3), 509–529.
- Smith, R., Jones, P., Briegleb, B., Bryan, F., Danabasoglu, G., Dennis, J., Dukowicz, J., Eden, C., Fox-Kemper, B., Gent, P., et al. (2010). The parallel ocean program (pop) reference manual ocean component of the community climate system model (ccsm) and community earth system model (cesm). *LAUR-01853*, 141, 1–140.
- Speich, S., Blanke, B., & Madec, G. (2001). Warm and cold water routes of an ogcm thermohaline conveyor belt. *Geophysical research letters*, 28(2), 311–314.

- Stommel, H. (1979). Determination of water mass properties of water pumped down from the Ekman layer to the geostrophic flow below. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 76(7), 3051–3055.
- Talley, L. D. (2011). *Descriptive physical oceanography: An introduction*. Academic press.
- Tamsitt, V., Drake, H. F., Morrison, A. K., Talley, L. D., Dufour, C. O., Gray, A. R., Griffies, S. M., Mazloff, M. R., Sarmiento, J. L., Wang, J., et al. (2017). Spiraling pathways of global deep waters to the surface of the southern ocean. *Nature communications*, 8(1), 172.
- Trani, M., Falco, P., Zambianchi, E., & Sallée, J.-B. (2014). Aspects of the antarctic circumpolar current dynamics investigated with drifter data. *Progress in Oceanography*, 125, 1–15.
- Waugh, D. W., Haine, T. W., & Hall, T. M. (2004). Transport times and anthropogenic carbon in the subpolar north atlantic ocean. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, 51(11), 1475–1491.
- Waugh, D. W., Hogg, A. M., Spence, P., England, M. H., & Haine, T. W. (2019). Response of southern ocean ventilation to changes in midlatitude westerly winds. *Journal of Climate*, 32(17), 5345–5361.
- Waugh, D., Hall, T., McNeil, B., Key, R., & Matear, R. (2006). Anthropogenic CO₂ in the oceans estimated using transit time distributions. *Tellus B: Chemical and Physical Meteorology*, 58(5), 376–389.

A Sensitivity Experiment ED05/ED05_{MLD}

A.1 Subduction Locations

Figure A.1: Left: Subduction locations for (a) MEAN, (c) ED05, and (e) ED05_{MLD}. The circumpolar red line marks the SAF. Black boxes show subduction zones: SP (35-70°S, 120-180°W), DP (45-70°S, 40-110°W), SA (20-45°S, 30°E-50°W), and SI (20-55°S, 40-180°E). Right: (b) zonal (logarithmic), (d) meridional, and (e) vertical distribution of subduction locations for MEAN (red), ED05 (blue), and ED05_{MLD} (purple).

A.2 Transit Times by Subduction Zones

Figure A.2: Statistics of the subduction zones DP (blue), SA (orange), SI (green) (see Fig. 3.1). **Column 1:** Proportions for (a) MEAN, (f) ED05, and (k) ED05_{MLD}. **Columns 2-4:** pTTD (solid) and G (dashed) per zone and experiment. Gray line marks total pTTD. **Column 4:** subduction depths by subduction zone and total (gray) for (e) MEAN, (j) ED05, and (o) ED05_{MLD}. Total mean ages are: 25.5y (ED05) and 22.6y (ED05_{MLD}).

B Subduction with Surface Condition

Figure B.1: Left: Surface contact (lower than 10m depth) locations for (a) MEAN and (c) ED04. The circumpolar red line marks the SAF. Black boxes show subduction zones: SP (35-70°S, 120-180°W), DP (45-70°S, 40-110°W), SA (20-45°S, 30°E-50°W), and SI (20-55°S, 40-180°E). Right: (b) zonal (logarithmic) and (d) meridional distribution of subduction locations for MEAN (red) and ED04 (blue)

C Orbiting Particles

Particles orbiting the ACC between subduction below the mixed layer and entrance of the AAIW can increase the estimated mean age, as they exhibit a prolonged transit time compared to direct pathways. To detect particles that orbit the ACC, I analyse particle trajectories regarding their zonal coverage and select those which pass by all longitudes. The relative proportion of particles orbiting the ACC differs throughout the experiments. While in MEAN 9.7% of particles orbit the ACC, ED04 (9.6%) shows a slightly, and ED04_{MLD} (6.5%) a significantly lower relative amount (Fig. C.1).

Experiment	All		Drake Passage		South Atlantic		South Indian Ocean	
	%	Γ [years]	%	Γ [years]	%	Γ [years]	%	Γ [years]
MEAN	9.67	53.8	11.28	47.4	4.42	58.7	7.98	71.7
ED04	9.60	54.2	9.71	50.8	4.14	55.7	7.56	68.5
ED04 _{MLD}	6.54	55.4	6.71	51.9	2.45	57.6	5.62	67.8

Table C.1: Volume weighted percentage and mean age of particles orbiting the ACC by subduction zones DP, SA, and SI for the experiments considered in this thesis. Percentage relative to particles in subduction zone.

Figure C.1: Drake Passage pTTD separated by orbiting/non-orbiting particles for (a) MEAN, (b) ED04, and (c) ED04_{MLD}. pTTD_{DP} bin size is 1 year, all DP particles in blue, orbiting particles in dark blue, non-orbiting particles in green. Dashed lines describe the Inverse Gaussian fit, with mean age Γ , width Δ , and rel. deviation ϵ .

The estimated mean age Γ for orbiting particles is remarkably high, exceeding the total mean age by 22–33 years. Throughout experiments, Γ is comparable for each subduction zone, with a maximum relative difference below 10%. The DP zone incorporates the highest proportion of orbiting particles, the SA zone the lowest. Γ_{DP} is lowest with ~ 50 years, Γ_{SI} is highest with ~ 70 years (Tab. C.1). Orbiting particles originating in the DP zone show the highest relative contribution of all zones. However, the overall contribution, even to the second peak of the MEAN pTTD_{DP}, is marginal. Nonetheless, as for the high transit times of orbiting particles, they increase the DP mean age by about 2 years (Fig. C.1)

Eidesstattliche Versicherung

Hiermit versichere ich an Eides statt, dass ich die Arbeit eigenständig verfasst habe. Ich habe keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt sowie wörtliche und sinngemäße Zitate kenntlich gemacht. Die Arbeit hat in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form noch keiner Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegen. Ich bin mit der Ausstellung der Arbeit in der Fachbibliothek einverstanden.

Hamburg

29.10.2024, Simon Schäfers (Matr. 7166528)